

A Medicine Cold Chain Monitor System Based on LoRa Wireless Technology

Lin Tao

School of Computer Science &
Information Engineering
Shanghai Institute of Technology
Shanghai, China

Liu Yunxiang

School of Computer Science &
Information Engineering
Shanghai Institute of Technology
Shanghai, China

Abstract: In the course of transportation of medical drugs, the requirements for temperature and humidity are high. We should strictly control it within a certain range, otherwise the deterioration of drugs will occur, which will lead to serious consequences. Therefore, a cold chain transport vehicle with temperature and humidity sensors should be used in medical transportation. This paper designs a wireless monitoring system based on LoRa technology, which can collect the data of temperature and humidity sensors on the transport vehicle in real time, and transmit them to the background through the LoRa gateway. Solve the technical problems of high power consumption and data upload failure. A wireless cold chain monitoring system with high data accuracy, strong expansibility and convenient networking is realized ensure the quality of drugs quantity safety.

Keywords: LoRa, Things of Internet, Cold Chain, Sensor, Temperature and Humidity

I. INTRODUCTION

Some medicines have strict requirements for temperature and humidity during storage and transportation. After being produced they should be refrigerated at low temperature throughout the whole process. From factory production to distribution center, and then from distribution center to hospitals at all levels, and finally to users, each link should be kept under certain low temperature conditions. And the requirement of humidity is very strict. So these drugs need to be transported in cold chain. Cold Chain Transport Vehicle is a kind of special vehicle which can keep the temperature of the carriage during driving. It is specially used for the transportation of medicines requiring refrigeration. During the transportation of drugs requiring refrigeration, the temperature and humidity of the drugs should be monitored continuously. However, at present, there is often a situation that temperature and humidity are not within the required range in the transportation of refrigerated drugs, which may be caused by the negligence of drug transporters or by insufficient refrigeration conditions, etc. This requires that the temperature and humidity of refrigerated drugs should be monitored in the whole

process of transportation. But the existing cold-chain temperature and humidity monitoring system cannot meet the requirements of vaccine transportation in CDC at all. It needs new technology to break through and support.

The technological development level of foreign pharmaceutical cold chain logistics is relatively mature, and the developed countries generally have modern pharmaceutical cold chain logistics technology. The temperature control system is equipped with RFID and GPS in the United States, and barcode technology and temperature sensor technology are used in Japan to monitor the quality of medical cold chain logistics service in real time. At the same time, Japan has also introduced in-vehicle map system to plan logistics distribution routes for medical cold-chain distribution vehicles, which greatly reduces the in-transit time of logistics, and has a high efficiency of medical cold-chain logistics distribution.

At present, the monitoring technology of temperature and humidity for drug transport vehicles in our country is mainly realized by placing temperature and humidity sensors. The sensors are connected with the gateway of

drug transport vehicles by wired way. The gateway transmits temperature and humidity data to the management platform of backstage through wireless data network. There are obvious shortcomings in this way. Firstly, the number of sensors connected by wired connection mode is limited. Generally, there are eight wires connected, that is, only eight temperature and humidity sensors. This number is far from enough. A cold chain truck usually carries 70 boxes of vaccines, with two temperatures in each box. Degree and humidity sensors require at least 140 connections, so the wired method cannot solve the problem of accurate temperature and humidity measurement. In addition, the wired transmission mode needs to punch holes in the carriage, which will destroy the refrigerated carriage box, resulting in the temperature affected by the outside world. Cable mode will also bring inconvenience to the installation personnel, and the routing in the carriage will affect the placement of drugs. The analysis of the shortcomings of wired mode makes it easy to think of using wireless mode to collect temperature and humidity. Nowadays, there are many ways of wireless transmission. Which way is the best one to use is also a question to be considered.

The temperature and humidity monitoring system of cold chain logistics designed in this paper adopts LoRa wireless transmission technology. LoRa technology was first developed by French company Cycleo (founded in 2009) as a patented spread spectrum wireless modulation technology. In 2012, Cycleo was acquired by Semtech for about \$5 million. After the acquisition, Semtech jointly launched the LoRa Alliance with Actility, Cisco and IBM in February 2015 to promote the participation of other companies in LoRa Ecology. After more than three years of development, the LoRa Alliance currently has more than 500 members worldwide and deploys LoRa networks in more than 100 countries worldwide.

LoRa technology has many advantages over other wireless transmission technologies. Firstly, from the technical point of view, compared with the NB-IoT scheme with higher cost and energy consumption, users can complete LoRa network deployment without relying on operators, which is not only faster in deployment, but also lower in cost. LoRa technology has obvious advantages in enclosed areas such as districts, farms and industrial parks, especially in indoor and underground environments where NB-IoT signals

are weak. Because of this "lightweight" construction advantage, the layout of LoRa scheme is actually more extensive. LoRa technology has a very competitive advantage. LoRa's autonomous advantage is obvious. Users can control the network quality independently, optimize and supplement the network coverage quickly, and operate independently, grasp the operation data in their own hands, and expand the network according to business needs.

LoRa technology based equipment acceptance sensitivity is astonishing - 148 dbm. Compared with other advanced sub-GHz chips in the industry, the highest acceptance sensitivity is improved by more than 20 db, which ensures the reliability of network connection. It uses LFM Spread Spectrum Modulation technology, which maintains the same low power characteristics as FSK (Frequency Shift Keying) modulation, significantly increases communication distance, improves network efficiency and eliminates interference, that is, the terminals of different spread spectrum sequences will not interfere with each other even if they use the same frequency at the same time. The concentrator/Gateway (concentrator/Gateway) developed on this basis can receive and process data from multiple nodes in parallel, greatly expanding the capacity of the system. Linear spread spectrum has been used in military and space communications for decades, because it can achieve long communication distance and interference robustness, and Lora is the first low-cost implementation for commercial purposes. With the introduction of Lora, the situation in the field of embedded wireless communication has changed completely. This technology changes the traditional way of compromise between transmission distance and power consumption, and provides a simple communication system with long distance, long battery life, large capacity and low cost.

Through comparative analysis, it is found that LoRa wireless temperature and humidity data acquisition terminal based on Lora technology can realize rapid deployment by using Lora narrowband Internet of Things wireless communication mode. The signal penetration performance of Lora technology is good. It can not only collect and monitor the temperature and humidity of cold chain logistics vehicle carriage in real time, but also monitor the loading box. Real-time data acquisition of temperature and humidity is carried out. The information of temperature, humidity, equipment number, voltage value, longitude and latitude is transmitted to the equipment management platform

through Lora gateway. The collected data is checked on the equipment management platform, and the data that is not received is promptly notified to the terminal for retransmitting, which is gathered to large scale. Data trusted platform, which processes the received data and data mining. At the same time, the data of temperature and humidity acquisition terminal can be read directly and submitted to customers, and can be compared with the data on the large data trusted platform to verify the authenticity and non-modifiability of the real-time data collected. At the same time, the data stored on the large data platform can be processed by the block chain-based storage technology. Trusted operation of existing platform.

In this paper a cold chain monitoring system has been proposed based on LoRa wireless technology. It takes temperature and humidity wireless collection terminal as the core, Lora gateway and equipment management platform as the communication basis, monitors the cold chain transport vehicle, obtains the temperature and humidity of drugs in the cold chain vehicle, and tracks the trajectory of the vehicle. Early prediction, real-time detection and early warning of abnormalities, warning of intervention and loss reduction, and realizing intelligent cold chain logistics with retrospective afterwards.

Fig.1. Usage scene

II.SYSTEM STRUCTURE

The usage scenario of the system is shown in Fig. 1. After the drug is produced, it is stored in the cold storage. When it needs to be transported to the user, it is transported by the refrigerated truck. Generally, each refrigerated truck can transport 70 boxes of medicines, each box of medicines. Two temperature and humidity

collection terminals are placed. The terminal has a built-in LoRa wireless module and a temperature and humidity sensor. The sensor detects the temperature and humidity data in the medicine box and uploads the data to the LoRa gateway through the LoRa wireless module. The LoRa gateway is installed in the refrigerated vehicle. In the compartment, each transport vehicle has only one gateway, and all the temperature and humidity collection terminals in the vehicle upload temperature and humidity data to the gateway. The gateway has a 4G/3g/2G module, which can uniformly collect the collected collection terminal data to the background management system

The system is mainly composed of three devices and two background software. The three devices are temperature and humidity collection terminal, LoRa gateway and portable management terminal. The two background software are composed of background management platform and big data analysis platform. The design structure and function of each device and software are described in detail below.

A. Wireless Intelligent Temperature and Humidity Monitoring Terminal

The terminal is placed in the medicine box of the cold chain transport vehicle for data acquisition of temperature and humidity in the outer space. The terminal has battery power supply, can collect and report the voltage value of the battery, and supports UART, I2C and other data communication interfaces. Built-in integrated LoRaWANTM protocol stack follows LoRaWANTM Specification 1.0.1 Class A/Class C standard. The design structure of the intelligent terminal is shown in Figure 1. When the gateway fails to report data to the gateway, the device can store 8000 data locally, which is equivalent to 7 days of data collection. Due to the extremely cold and humid environment in the cold storage and refrigerated trucks, the collection terminal has a waterproof design that can measure temperatures between -20 and 60 °C

Fig.2. Structure diagram of temperature and humidity acquisition terminal

B. LoRa Gateway

After the data is collected by the monitoring terminal, if it is directly uploaded to the management platform on the cloud, each data collection terminal has the data network access capability, and the wireless data chip is included in the device, which increases the cost of the terminal. It also increases the power consumption of the terminal, and in the system, the number of collection terminals will be very large. Direct access to the device management platform on the network will lead to congestion of the management platform and frequent data transmission failure, so in each refrigerated transport vehicle in the system. A LoRa gateway is installed to collect data of all the collection terminals on the vehicle, and then uniformly sent to the management platform through the 4G network.

LoRa gateway is an 8-channel, high-performance, industrial-grade LoraWAN intelligent gateway device based on the LoRa WAN protocol. At the same time, it has real-time WebSocket and OpenAPI RESTful access modes. It also supports the data transmission of 4G and Ethernet, and supports the input power supply of adapter power supply. In the absence of carrier wireless network environment, Lora Gateway supports WiFi access upstream capability. When the LoRa gateway is in an area where there is no wireless network, the reported data is temporarily stored in the local storage of the gateway, and the LoRa gateway supports storage of 10,000 data, which is equivalent to 10 days of data.

Fig.3. Structure of LoRa Gateway

C. Portable management terminal

Another device is the portable management terminal product. The portable management terminal product is

based on LoRa and BT communication technology. It is a terminal product that collects the data of intelligent temperature and humidity terminal products directly and wirelessly. The product embedded minimum system module, LoRa module, Bluetooth module, using USB interface power supply mode, through LoRa wireless technology point-to-point direct reading of data collected by intelligent temperature and humidity recorder, to ensure the authenticity of data and direct viewing for customers, through Bluetooth and mobile phone interconnection, display data content.

The main function of this device is that when the temperature and humidity acquisition terminal is far away from LoRa gateway, the actual temperature and humidity data can not be reported to the management platform. In order to confirm the temperature and humidity in the medicine box, users need to use the portable management terminal, which is used with the APP on the mobile phone, and the mobile phone is blue. The tooth port is connected to the portable terminal, and the portable terminal connects the temperature and humidity acquisition terminal through the LoRa interface, as shown in the figure 4.

Fig.4. Use scenarios about portable management terminal

III. DATA RETRANSMIT MECHANISM

In the process of data transmission, the temperature and humidity acquisition terminal will not receive the data frames from the terminal upstream in the background because of the airport collision or the gateway dropping off. Wireless transmission technology often encounters such problems. If the data is incomplete, the management platform on the cloud will lose the temperature and humidity data of drugs for a period of time and lose the significance of the whole process supervision. The system adopts the equipment management platform to lead frame loss and retransmit,

and the terminal periodically uploads data. The background detects that the terminal data is not uploaded on time. In the receiving window of the data frame uploaded normally by the terminal, the downlink retransmit instruction TH_RESEND_CMD_ID 0x01 is used. After receiving the retransmit instruction, the terminal module adds the data packet for the next data transmission. Add the data frames that need to be retransmitted, pack them together and send them to the background. When the data packets are received by the background, the retransmitted data will be parsed out and added to the original data loss location until all the data frames that need to be retransmitted are uploaded to the background.

Fig.5. data retransmit mechanism

IV. TIMESHARE UPLOAD MECHANISM

Because there are many temperature and humidity collecting terminals distributed in each refrigerated transport vehicle, and there are also many vehicles transporting at the same time, so a large number of terminals will send temperature and humidity data to the background. With the increase of equipment, the chance of collision of uploading and sending packets will increase, and even the number of times will occur in serious cases. Packets will fail to send, resulting in a large number of retransmissions waiting to be sent. The data acquisition cycle of this system is 2 minutes. This acquisition frequency is much higher than other Internet of Things application scenarios. Therefore, we must design a mechanism to improve the success rate of data upload and reduce the retransmit rate. At the same time, such a mechanism will also decrease. Low power consumption of acquisition terminal. The system designs a time-sharing upload mechanism. The equipment management platform transmits data according to the ID calculation module of the terminal module. According to the time when the ID address

calculation module transmits data, the backstage packages the calculated time slice under the instruction data package and sends it to the intelligent temperature and humidity terminal. The intelligent temperature and humidity terminal parses the data. After the time slice, upload data according to the time slice instructions to ensure that the millisecond interval of module sending data does not conflict, and further reduce the module sending data gap conflict.

Fig.6. timeshare upload process

V. CAD DETECTION MECHANISM

CAD is Channel Activity Detected CAD is use to monitor the working state of the frequency point, and then determine whether the received data has Lora preamble, if there is a receive, if there is no or wrong preamble, then close the receive, making the module more power-saving. The temperature and humidity terminal uses CAD to detect whether the management terminal is sending data. If it detects that the

management terminal is sending data, it opens the reception, receives the instructions sent by the management terminal, and parses and replies the instructions. The temperature and humidity terminal should be in the mode of CAD detection. It needs the management terminal to send the instruction of opening CAD to the equipment management background. After receiving the instruction, the terminal opens the CAD monitor, and then the management terminal sends the instruction to the temperature and humidity terminal. The temperature and humidity terminal can receive the instruction, parse and reply. When the temperature and humidity terminal CAD is opened, different intervals can be set to monitor a CAD reception.

Fig.7. CAD Mechanism

Fig.8. awaken and power

VI. EQUIPMENT MANAGEMENT PLATFORM

Drug temperature and humidity data are sent to the cloud device management platform via the LoRa gateway via the 4G mobile network. Equipment management platform should satisfy a series of requirements of data acquisition, storage, re-display and transmission in the Internet of Things. It should ensure that data acquisition and storage can be securely and extensively accessed to the base station, guarantee 7*24 uninterrupted service, and develop standard interfaces for display and transmission, so as to ensure that the data of terminal module is not lost within 10 days. Replace missing data. It can monitor and manage the temperature and humidity acquisition terminal and base station network in real time, monitor and display the operation status of the equipment, monitor and predict

the power consumption of the equipment, and support the remote version upgrade of the acquisition terminal and Lora base station in the future.

When the business platform obtains the temperature, humidity, terminal voltage, device ID number, longitude and latitude, collection time and other information of temperature and humidity acquisition terminal and base station, it can carry out real-time processing, alarm for the terminal exceeding the pre-set threshold of temperature and humidity, statistical analysis of temperature and humidity data, and judgment of drug storage and start-up. Whether the temperature and humidity control requirements are strictly met in the process of transportation, transportation, unloading, handover and so on, power consumption alarm should be given to the terminal which is about to deplete electric energy, and equipment replacement should be carried out as soon as possible to avoid losing data. Through the analysis of GPS latitude and longitude information, the trajectory, distance and time information of cold chain vehicles can be analyzed. The efficient management of cold chain vehicles can be realized, and the scientific route planning can be realized by combining with the transportation task allocation software. Through the analysis of equipment ID number, it can be judged which vaccine boxes are loaded and unloaded at which location, and the prediction of vehicle spare space. It can be combined with cold chain logistics to share transportation and improve transportation efficiency.

VII. CONCLUSION

After practical use, the medical cold chain monitoring system based on LoRa technology is well applied in the vaccine cold chain transportation system of the State Pharmaceutical Group. After one year's use, the problem of temperature and humidity monitoring in the vaccine transportation can be completely solved. The data can be preserved and analyzed from bottom to bottom, and the epidemic can be realized for the State Pharmaceutical Group. The seedling supervision provides technical support.

REFERENCES

- [1] LoRa Alliance, "LoRa Alliance 2017 end of year report." Available: <https://lora-alliance.org/sites/default/files/2018-04/LoRa-Alliance-Annual-Report.pdf>. [Online; accessed Mar. 15, 2019].
- [2] LoRa Alliance, "LoRaWAN What is it? A technical overview of LoRa and LoRaWAN." Available: <https://lora-alliance.org/sites/default/files/2018-04/what-is-lorawan.pdf>. [Online; accessed Mar. 15, 2019].
- [3] J. de Carvalho Silva, J. J. P. C. Rodrigues, A. M. Alberti, P. Solic, and A. L. L. Aquino, "Lorawan — a low power wan

- protocol for internet of things: A review and opportunities,” in International Multidisciplinary Conference on Computer and Energy Science, pp. 1–6, July 2017
- [4] Philip A. Catherwood, David Steele, Mike Little, Stephen McComb, and James McLaughlin, “A Community-based IoT Personalized Wireless Healthcare Solution Trial”, in IEEE Journal of Translational Engineering in Health and Medicine, pp. vol 6, 08 May 2018
- [5] M. Kuroda and M. Fukahori, “Affordable M2M enabled e-health using standard BAN technology,” in 2014 IEEE Healthcare Inn. Conf., pp.276-279.
- [6] Rashmi Sharan Sinha, Yiqiao Wei and Seung-Hoon Hwang, “A survey on LPWA technology: LoRa and NB-IoT”, in ICT Express, pp. 14-21, Vol 3, Issue 1, March 2017
- [7] Martin Bor, John Vidler and Utz Roedig, "LoRa for the Internet of Things", in International Conference on Embedded Wireless Systems and Networks (EWSN) Graz, Austria, pp.361-366 15–17 Feb 2016
- [8] Andrew J Wixted, Peter Kinnaird, Hadi Larijani, Alan Tait, Ali Ahmadi and Niall Strachan, "Evaluation of LoRa and LoRaWAN for wireless sensor networks", in IEEE SENSORS, Oct 2016
- [9] Song GuoGuiyi, WeiYang, XiangXiaodong, LinPascal and Lorenz, “Building Low-Cost Gateways and Devices for Open LoRa IoT Test-Beds”, in Testbeds and Research Infrastructures for the Development of Networks and Communities, HANGZHOU, pp.70-80, Jun 2016
- [10] Mads Lauridsen, Huan Nguyen, Benny Vejlgaard, Istvan Z. Kovacs, Preben Mogensen and Mads Sorensen, "Coverage Comparison of GPRS, NB-IoT, LoRa, and SigFox in a 7800 km² Area", in 2017 IEEE 85th Vehicular Technology Conference (VTC Spring)
- [11] Juha Petäjälä, Konstantin Mikhaylov, Matti Hämäläinen and Jari Iinatti, “View All Authors Evaluation of LoRa LPWAN technology for remote health and wellbeing monitoring”, in 2016 10th International Symposium on Medical Information and Communication Technology (ISMICT), 20-23 March 2016
- [12] Oratile Khutsoane, Bassey Isong, Adnan M. Abu-Mahfouz, “IoT devices and applications based on LoRa/LoRaWAN”, in IECON 2017 - 43rd Annual Conference of the IEEE Industrial Electronics Society, Nov. 2017
- [13] Sinha R., Wei Y., Hwang S. “A survey on LPWA technology: LoRa and NB-IoT”, in J. ICT Express, pp. 14-21, Vol 3 2017
- [14] Kais Mekki, Eddy Bajic, Frederic Chaxel and Fernand Meyer, “A comparative study of LPWAN technologies for large-scale IoT deployment”, in ICT Express, pp.1-7, Vol 5, Issue 1, Mar 2019
- [15] Martin C. Bor, Utz Roedig, Thimo Voigt and Juan M. Alonso, “Do LoRa Low-Power Wide-Area Networks Scale?”, in MSWiM '16 Proceedings of the 19th ACM International Conference on Modeling, Analysis and Simulation of Wireless and Mobile Systems, Pages 59-67, Nov 2016
- [16] Alexandru Lavric and Valentin Popa, “Internet of Things and LoRa™ Low-Power Wide-Area Networks: A survey”, in 2017 International Symposium on Signals, Circuits and Systems (ISSCS), July 2017
- [17] Nur Hayati and Muhammad Suryanegara, “The IoT LoRa system design for tracking and monitoring patient with mental disorder”, in 2017 IEEE International Conference on Communication, Networks and Satellite (Comnetsat), Oct 2017
- [18] Dong Hyun Kim, Jung Bin Park, Jae Ho Shin and Jong Deok Kim, “Design and implementation of object tracking system based on LoRa”, in 2017 International Conference on Information Networking (ICOIN), Apr 2017
- [19] Dong Hyun Kim, Jun Young Lim and Jong Deok Kim, “Low-Power, Long-Range, High-Data Transmission Using Wi-Fi and LoRa”, in 2016 6th International Conference on IT Convergence and Security (ICITCS), Sep 2016